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Research Article

Improvement And Evaluation of Polyherbal Soap Incorporating Potato, Rice and Batak Onion Extract

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ABSTRACT

Herbal cleansers, frequently known as common cleansers, are made from plant-based fixings and botanical extracts. Bacterial skin diseases are most common among individuals, requiring critical attention for treatment and too for keeping up solid skin. The point and objective of the display consider are to advancement and evaluation of polyherbal cleanser joining potato, rice and Batak onion extract. Home grown cleanser planning is a medication it contains against- bacterial, anti-ageing anti-oxidant, anti-septic properties which basically employments of portion of plant like seeds, rhizomes. nuts and pulps to treatment for a harm or illness or to accomplish wellbeing. The simple accessibility of plants and their effectiveness makes a difference producer with cost-effective benefits and with less or no side effects.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal medication has its beginnings in old societies. It includes the therapeutic utilize of plants to treat illness and improve common wellbeing and prosperity. A few herbs have strong (effective) fixings and ought to be taken with the same level of caution as pharmaceutical medicines. In reality, numerous pharmaceutical medicines are based on man-made forms of actually happening compounds found in plants. For occasion, the heart pharmaceutical digitalis was inferred from the foxglove plant. Home grown

medications contain dynamic fixings. The dynamic fixings of numerous home grown arrangements are as however obscure. A few pharmaceutical medicines are based on a single dynamic fixing inferred from a plant source. Specialists of home-grown medication accept that a dynamic fixing can lose its affect or gotten to be less secure if utilized in separation from the rest of the plant. Concurring to home grown pharmaceutical professionals, the impact of the entirety plant is more prominent than its parts. Pundits contend that the nature of home grown

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pharmaceutical makes it troublesome to allow a measured measurement of a dynamic fixing.

Skin is exceptionally critical for all wellbeing care experts to have essential data around the structure and work of human skin. Skin is too called cutaneous film. In grown-ups the skin has a surface range extending from 1.2 to 2.2 m². Skin has two sorts, hair-bearing skin that covers much of the body and smooth skin as that of palms of hands and soles of feet Skin is the most uncovered portion of the body to the daylight, natural contamination and moreover utilized to a few securities against the pathogen.

Soap is a salt of greasy corrosive utilized in an assortment of cleansing and greasing up items. Cleansers are surfactant more often than not utilized for washing and showering and other sorts of housekeeping. Cleansers are utilized to expel earth counting clean microorganism, strains terrible smells from the body. Commercial cleanser as a rule are made up of harmful mercury aluminium, barium, bis-phenol, plastics and other chemicals, which are retained into the body through inside organs from vaporization of the chemicals as well as skin assimilation with negative side impacts.

Herbal soap Herbal cleanser planning is a medication it contains hostile to- bacterial, anti-ageing anti-oxidant, clean properties which primarily employments of portion of plant like seeds, rhizomes. nuts and pulps to treatment for a harm or malady or to accomplish wellbeing. Home grown cleanser do not contain the counterfeit colors, flavors, fluorides etc., when compared to the substance of commercial cleanser. Herbs are the characteristic items generally found in the treatment of nearly all maladies and skin issues owing to their tall restorative esteem, taken a toll compelling ness, accessibility and compatibility. Azadirachta indica is one the best trees in India, which known for its restorative properties. In natural products and seeds are the source of neem

oil. It is utilized to treat most few common issues that the individuals confront. The Aloe Vera has been known and utilized for centuries for its wellbeing, excellence, restorative and skin care properties. These days most habitually aloe Vera utilized in the field of cosmetology. Aloe Vera contains 75 possibly dynamic constituents. Curcuma longa having properties like photo security, anti-ageing, anti-wrinkle, moisturizing, Anti-oxidants. astringent, anti-microbial and anti-inflammatory action. Later considers illustrate that the curcumin is fabulous for wrinkles and can control the aggravation and the arrangement of free radicles. Herbal pharmaceuticals are in more demand than their synthetic counterparts for a variety of reasons, including the following:

- Minimal Adverse Effects
- Enhanced safety and effectiveness
- Easily accessible
- Improved compatibility with other ingredients
- significant curative effect
- Increased tolerability for all skin tones
- Cost effective

Benefits of Polyherbal Soap:

1. **Natural Ingredients:** Polyherbal soaps contain natural ingredients that are generally free from harmful chemicals, making them gentler on the skin and reducing the risk of irritation and allergic reactions.
2. **Antibacterial Properties:** Many herbs used in these soaps, such as neem and tea tree oil, have strong antibacterial properties, helping to cleanse the skin effectively and reduce the risk of infections.
3. **Moisturizing Effects:** Herbal ingredients like aloe vera and honey are known for their moisturizing properties, which help to keep the skin hydrated and prevent dryness.
4. **Antioxidant Rich:** Ingredients such as turmeric and green tea are rich in antioxidants, which can help to protect the skin from free

radicals, thereby reducing the signs of aging and promoting healthy skin.

5. Soothing and Anti-inflammatory: Herbs like chamomile and calendula have soothing and anti-inflammatory properties, which can help to calm irritated skin and reduce redness and swelling.
6. Improved Complexion: Regular use of polyherbal soap can improve skin tone and texture, thanks to ingredients like sandalwood and saffron, which are known for their skin-brightening properties.
7. Acne Prevention and Treatment: Ingredients such as neem and tea tree oil are effective in preventing and treating acne due to their antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties.

Aroma therapeutic Benefits: Essential oils from herbs like lavender, rosemary, and eucalyptus not only provide a pleasant fragrance but also offer aroma therapeutic benefits, promoting relaxation and reducing stress.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sodium hydroxide was secured from Qualigens Fine chemicals, Mumbai. Neem oil, Tulasi oil, and Coconut oil were obtained from the nearby advertise. Glycerine, Propylene Glycol, and Sodium lauryl sulfate were obtained from Thermo fisher logical India Pvt ltd., Mumbai. Triethanolamine was secured from Loba Chemie Pvt ltd., Mumbai. The other whole chemicals utilized were of analytical grade.

➤ Arrangement of leaf powder

Fresh clear out of neem and batak onion were washed with water completely to evacuate the soil and unwanted molecule. Amide the drying

prepare, the takes off were cleared out beneath daylight for three days then clears out were ground to powder form.

• Planning of potato powder

Fresh potatoes were washed with water completely to evacuate soil and undesirable particles then potatoes were daintily cut in chips shape and at that point dried beneath sun for around one week and then with the offer assistance of mechanical processor fine powder was gotten and passed through a 40 Micron sieve and test were put away in discuss tight container.

• Planning of rice powder

Rinse the rice altogether beneath running water to expel any earth or pollutions until the water runs clear. Spread the depleted rice on a clean cloth or paper towels and let it discuss dry for a few hours. Transfer the somewhat soggy rice to a processor or blender. Pound the rice to a fine powder.

Preparation Of Cleanser Base

- For planning the cleanser base, to begin with of all take 75 ml coconut oil in a 500 ml beaker.
- Put the coconut oil in the water shower and stir-boil it until a solid consistency shapes at temperature between 40 to 45 °C.
- At that point take 13.20 gm sodium hydroxide break up in 24 ml refined water in an another container and mixed properly.
- After planning this arrangement was included gradually in coconut oil blend with steady Stirring.

The blend wash bubble at 40-45 °C until base consistency is achieved and at that point this Blend was used as a cleanser base.

Table1: Preparation of soap base

Sr. no.	Ingredients	Quantity	Role/Uses
1	Sodium hydroxide	13.20ml	Lye
2	Coconut oil	75ml	Anti-ageing Soothe skin
3	Distilled water	24ml	Aqueous vehicle

➤ **Formulation of polyherbal soap**

- Take 60 ml of soap base in a beaker and put on water bath at 45°C
- Then add the all ingredients with continuous stirring in to soap base.
- Boil the mixture on the water bath at 45°C and soap mixture is prepared.

- Prepared soap mixture is filled in soap molds and mold is put in the refrigerator for 15 minutes.
- After solidification cut the soap mold using cutter or blade.
- Then obtained herbal soap

Fig1. Prepared Anti-microbial herbal soap

Evaluation Test

❖ **Organoleptic parameter:**

Table2: Organoleptic Parameter

Sr. No.	Parameter	Results
1	Color	Green
2	Odor	Pleasant
3	Texture	Smooth
4	State	Solid
5	Nature	Neutral

❖ **pH test:**

➤ **Procedure:**

- Froth of the soap was collected from the surface by dissolving some portion of it in water.
- pH paper was dipped in the froth to determine its nature.
- Color of the pH paper was compare with standard pH color chart.

☐ **Nature test**

➤ **Procedure**

- Froth of the soap was collected from the surface of soap by dissolving some portion in water.
- Litmus paper was dipped in the froth to determine its nature.

☐ **Foam height test**

➤ **Procedure:**

- 0.5 gram of sample was taken dispersed in 25 ml distilled water.

- Then transfer it into 100 ml measuring cylinder volume was make up to 50 ml with water 25 strokes were given and stand till aqueous volume measured up to 50 ml and measure the foam height.

☐ **Foam Retention test**

➤ **Procedure:**

- 25 ml of the 1% soap solution was taken into a 100 ml measuring cylinder.
- The cylinder was covered with hand and shaken 10 times.
- The volume of foam at 1min intervals for min was recorded.

☐ **Melting point test**

➤ **Procedure:**

- Small amount of herbal soap was taken in capillary.

- Capillary tube was attached to the thermometer using string.
- Thiele's tube was filled with liquid paraffin and the above assembly was immersed till 1/4th of the capillary tube was dipped in liquid paraffin.
- Rubber stopper was used to closed the end of Thiele's tube.

□ **High temperature stability test.**

➤ **Procedure:**

- ❖ Liquid soap wasted to stand at 50°C for one week.
- ❖ The stability of liquid soap observed during this period
- ❖ The sample which was homogenous and stable liquid after standing was indicated and stable and the sample in which the crystals were roughed and sample in which the precipitation was caused.
- ❖ Then liquid was settle down at bottom.

❖ **Antibacterial activity:**

This consider points to check the antibacterial action of different branded cleansers against microbes that are regularly display in the environment. The proposed ponder incorporates determination of most common bacterial strains from the environment. Recognizable proof of bacterial strains was done by standard

microbiological procedures, which incorporate gram recoloring, biochemical testing and advanced identification by expository profile file. Assurance of negligible inhibitory concentration and minimum bactericidal action of strains was performed by tube and small scale titration method. Antibacterial cleansers appeared superior MIC in comparison with excellence cleansers. The most resistant bacterium to all the cleansers is Klebsiella pneumonia and Pseudomonas aeruginosa. It is self-evident that antibacterial cleansers have the antibacterial specialists that can either slaughter or restrain the bacterial cells. It might be conceivable that a few bacterial strains ended up safe which leads to their survival even at tall concentrations of soaps.

□ **Isolation of bacteria**

All tests were appropriately weakened and spread on the supplement agar. The pH was balanced to 7.0, incubated for 24 h at 37°C. At that point immunization was made on supplement agar plates and brooded at 37°C for 24 h. The most plenteous strain of the tests was chosen, gram recolored, and then purified on modern plate of supplement agar.

❖ **Preparation of agar method:**

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity (taken)
1	Meat extract	10gm
2	Peptone	10gm
3	Sodium hydroxide	5gm
4	Refined water	100ml
5	Agar	2-4%

• **Distinguishing proof of disconnected bacteria**

Identification of microscopic organisms was done by utilizing distinctive biochemical tests. These tests were based on the gram recolor response of bacterial strains. Tests incorporates, oxidase test, catalase test, urease test, motility test, corrosive generation from glucose, mannitol, sucrose, lactose, maltose, coagulase test, DNase test, indole test, eosin methylene blue test, triple sugar press responses, methyl ruddy test, voges proskauer test.

• **Anti- Fungal Test:**

Disk Dissemination Test (Kirby-Bauer Strategy):

Principle: This test assesses the capacity of an antimicrobial substance (in this case, your poly herbal cleanser) to repress the development of microorganisms, counting organisms, by dissemination of the active components from the test fabric into an agar medium.

Procedure: Candida albicans culture is equitably spread on the surface of a Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) plate. Sterile channel paper disks are at that point impregnated with your poly home grown cleanser extract and put on to the agar surface. The plate is at that point brooded. If the cleanser has

antifungal properties, it will make a zone of restraint around the disk where contagious development is hindered. Interpretation: The distance across of the zone of restraint is measured and compared to built up measures or control substances. A bigger zone shows more grounded antifungal activity.

❖ **RESULT AND DISCUSSION**

Table3: Organoleptic character of herbal soap

Sr. No.	Parameter	Results
1	Color	Green
2	Odor	Pleasant
3	Texture	Smooth
4	State	Solid
5	Nature	Neutral

After being extricated utilizing ethanol and water, the extractive values of the unrefined drugs, Batak onion and neem were found to be 4.2 % and 5.6 %, separately, upon total drying on the water bath. The assessment comes about of the diverse parameters for these details are as follows:

• **Organoleptic character of herbal soap:**

• **Physical evaluation:**

Each of the five formulations had a green color and a pleasant scent. The texture was smooth, glossy, non-gritty, and had an opaque appearance. The preparations were uniform and simple to clean.

• **pH:**

The pH of all the tested formulations were found to be in the range of 6.9-7.5

• **Foam height:**

The foam height in all the tested formulations of herbal soap were given in the table (Table). From the observation table, it was found that, the F-4 formulation have good foam height as compared to other formulations.

• **Foam retention:**

According to the observation table (table same of foam height), the F-4 formulation has a better retention time than the others, which was almost stable for 8 minutes. So, F-4 formulation can be considered as good on this parameter also.

• **Antibacterial assay:**

The antimicrobial assay revealed that the F-4 herbal soap formulation is effective at inhibiting the growth of microorganisms, similar to the marketed product. As a result, we can conclude that the F-4 formulation is suitable for bulk preparation and subsequent application.

• **Nature test:**

after performing natures test the nature of herbal soap is found to be neutral in nature.

• **The melting point test:**

the maximum melting point of the prepared herbal soap which shows result 130°C– 135 °C.

• **High temperature stability**

was found to be 42High temperature stability test.

• **Determination of moisture content**

Weight of china dish: 126.04gm

Weight of soap: 10gm

Weight of both: 136gm

Weight of china dish after heating: 133.6 gm

Moisture content = $\frac{\text{different in weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \times 100 = \frac{136 - 133.6}{136} \times 100$

Moisture content = 2.05

Sr. No.	Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	pH	6.8	6.9	6.7	7	7.3
2	Foam Height Test	22cm	22.5cm	21cm	24cm	21cm
3	Foam Retention Time	2.4min	2min	3min	3.5min	2min
4	Melting Point	120°C	125°C	130°C	135°C	127°C

5	High Temperature Stability test	40°C	30°C	35°C	45°C	40°C
6	Moisture content	2	3.5	4	2.05	3

Fig2: Herbal Soap

CONCLUSION

In this project, we successfully developed and assessed a polyherbal soap incorporating extracts of potato, rice, and batak onion. The formulation process was meticulously designed to leverage the individual and synergistic benefits of these natural ingredients, resulting in a soap that is both effective and gentle on the skin. The potato extract provided essential vitamins and antioxidants that aid in skin nourishment and rejuvenation. Rice extract contributed its well-known moisturizing and anti-inflammatory properties, enhancing the soap's ability to hydrate and soothe the skin. Batak onion extract added potent antimicrobial and healing properties, making the soap particularly beneficial for individuals with acne-prone or sensitive skin. The polyherbal soap underwent rigorous testing for its physicochemical properties, including pH, lathering ability, and stability. Results indicated that the soap maintained an optimal pH balance suitable for all skin types, produced a rich and creamy lather, and demonstrated excellent stability over time. Sensory evaluation and user trials further validated the soap's efficacy, with participants reporting significant improvements in skin texture, hydration, and overall appearance. In conclusion, the integration of potato, rice, and batak onion

extracts into a polyherbal soap formulation has shown promising results, offering a natural, effective, and sustainable alternative to conventional skincare products. This study not only highlights the potential of utilizing botanical extracts in personal care products but also paves the way for further research and development in the field of herbal cosmetics. The successful creation and positive assessment of this polyherbal soap underscore its potential for commercial production and consumer acceptance.

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REFERENCES

1. JM, Jensen JM. The skin: An indispensable barrier. *Exp Dermatol* 2008; 17:1063-72.
2. Pushpa R, Mamta A, Sharma S. Phytochemical and antioxidant properties of various extracts of *Micheliachampaca* leaves. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci* 2019; 11:614.
3. Oyedele AO, Akinkunmi EO, Fabiyi DD, Orafidiya LO. Physicochemical properties and antimicrobial activities of soap formulations containing *Senna alata* and *Eugenia uniflora* leaf preparations. *J Med Plant Res* 2017; 11:778-87.

4. Esimone C, Nworu C, Ekong U, Okereke B. Evaluation of the antiseptic properties of Cassia alatabased herbal soap. *Internet J Alternate Med* 2007; 6:1-5.
5. Hunt JA. A short history of soap. *Pharm J* 1999; 263:985-9.
6. Ruckmani K, Krishnamoorthy R, Samuel S, Linda H, Kumari J. Formulation of herbal bath soap from Vitex negundo leaf extract. *J Chem Pharm Sci* 2014; 2:974-2115.
7. Afsar Z, Khanam S. Formulation and evaluation of poly herbal soap. *Int Res J Pharm* 2016; 7:54-7.
8. Kirtikar, K. R. Basu B.D., 1975. *Indian Medicinal Plants vol III*. Periodical experts, Delhi, 2327.
9. Sheth. N.R., 1988, M./Pharm Thesis, —pharmacognostical and phytochemical investigation of Ficus glomerata bark and Fractionation of hypoglycemic agent from Ficus glomerata bark | Saurashtra University.
10. N. Chopra., —*Indian Council of Medical Research*, 1955, 30, 27.
11. K. M. Nadkarni, A. K. Nadkarni., *Indian Materia Medica*, volume 2, (Popular prakashan Bombay, 3rd ed., 2000. 37.
12. K. R. Khandelwal., *Practical Pharmacognosy techniques and experiments.*, 13th edition, 2005, 157.
13. P. R. Rastogi and B. N. Melhotra., *Compendium of Indian Medicinal Plant*, Vol 3 Central drug research institute, Lucknow, 1999, 312.
14. Kandasamy R. Formulation of Herbal Bath Soap from Vitex negundo Leaf Extract. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2014; 2: 95-99.
15. Antignac E, Nohynek G J, Re T, Clouzeau J, Toutain H. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 2011; 49: 324– 341.
16. Solanki R. Treatment of skin diseases through medicinal plants in different regions of the world. *International Journal of Biomedical Research*. 2011; 2(1):
17. Saikia A.P., Ryakala V.K., Sharma P., Goswami P., Bora U. Ethnobotany of medicinal plants used by Assamese people for various skin ailments and cosmetics. *Journal of Ethno pharmacology*. 106(2), 2006; 106(2):149-157.
18. Shreya Talreja¹, Prof. Dr. Shashank Tiwari² & Archana Bharti³ Assistant Professor¹, Director² & Scholar³ Lucknow Model College of Pharmacy, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, June 2023 *European Chemical Bulletin* 12(8):2121-2141.
19. Selvamani M., Surya Prakash R., Siva Shankar D., Subash K., Siva Guru M., L. V. Vigneswaran", M. Senthil Kumar Sree Abirami College of Pharmacy, Coimbatore¹, formulation and evaluation of polyherbal soap, 19 Dec 2021, ISSN 2455-3301 *Wipmr*.
20. There U G, et al. Formulation of Hand Made Soap by using Goat Milk, *Interactional Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology*, 2022; 10(2): 955-960.
21. Joshi, et al. Fabrication and Valuation of Poly Herbal Soap Via Utilizing a Variety of Herbal Extracts, *IJCRT*, 2022; 10(3): 187-193.
22. Sudharani MV, et al. Formulation and Evaluation of Tridax Procumbens (L.) Herbal Soaps, *Journal of Pharmacy* 2023, 3(1):1-8.
23. Bark at Ali Khan et al., Review Article; Human skin, ageing and anti-oxidants; *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, January 2012; 6(1):1-6.
24. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Soap>
25. Nam Jeremiah Akuaden, L.Y. Chindo, Joel Ogboji: Formulation and Physicochemical and Antifungi Evaluation of Herbal Soaps of Azadiracta Indica and Ziziphus Mauritiana:

IOSR Journal of Applied Chemistry; August, 2019; 12(8):26-3.

26. Aiello A. E., Larson E. L., Levy S. B. Review Article; Consumer Antibacterial Soap. Effective or just risky? *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, September 2007;45(2): 137-147.
27. Ashlesha Ghanwat, Sachin Wayzod and Vanjire Divya; Research Article; Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal soap: Current Trends in Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Chemistry, April 2020; 2(2): 21-26..

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